

Thiotropolone T.T., a Chromogenic Reagent for the Determination of Rhodium, Palladium and Osmium

JAWAHAR LAL SHARMA, B. S. GARG, J. N. SRIVASTAVA and R. P. SINGH*

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110007

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Addition of thiotropolone (T.T.) solution to solutions of different platinum metals, viz., Rh(III), Pd(II) and Os(VIII), results in the formation of coloured complexes. Complexation takes place in cold with Pd(II), whereas the reactants have to be heated on a boiling water bath in case of Rh(III) and Os(VIII). Optimum conditions leading to the accurate determination of each metal have been established. Os(VIII)-T.T. complexation has been studied in aqueous medium, but Rh(III)-T.T. and Pd(II)-T.T. complexations have been studied in chloroform medium. The methods developed are simple, sensitive and compare well with existing methods known for these metals.

BEAMISH¹ and Boltz and Mellon² have given critical accounts of reagents employed for the spectrophotometric determination of rhodium, palladium and osmium. Some of the reagents known for these metals are : tin bromide⁴(Rh), thoron³(Rh), sulphanic acid⁴(Os) and tropolone^{5,6}(Rh, Pd).

The present communication reports methods for the spectrophotometric determination of rhodium, palladium and osmium with thiotropolone (T.T.). This reagent has already been used for the colorimetric determination of cobalt, nickel⁷ and platinum⁸. T.T. reacts with palladium(II) in cold forming a red coloured complex ($\lambda_{max} = 520$ nm), while heating is required in the case of rhodium(III) and osmium(VIII), whereby the formation of brown ($\lambda_{max} = 500$ nm) and brownish red ($\lambda_{max} = 540$ nm) complexes takes place respectively. The optimum conditions for the determination of each metal have been established and effect of other variables such as temperatures, pH and heating etc. has also been investigated in detail.

Experimental

Reagents and equipments : A Unicam, SP 600, spectrophotometer with optically matched glass cells of 10 mm optical path was used for absorbance measurements. A Metrohm (E-350) pH-meter with saturated calomel and a glass electrode assembly was employed for pH measurements.

Thiotropolone was synthesised by the method of Nozoe *et al.*^{9,10} and its stock solution (0.01M) was prepared in acetone. Stock solutions of rhodium(III) and palladium(II) were obtained by dissolving requisite amounts of the respective chlorides (Johnson Mathey, U.K.) in concentrated hydrochloric acid and diluting the solutions to give a final acidity of 1M. The solutions were further standardized by the

known gravimetric methods. A stock solution of osmium(VIII) was prepared by dissolving appropriate quantity of osmium tetroxide (Johnson Mathey, U.K.) in 2M sodium hydroxide solution and standardizing the solution by modified method of Klobbie. Working solutions were obtained by diluting the stock solutions, whenever required.

All other reagents used were of the reagent grade.

Preliminary investigations : It was observed that in osmium-T.T. and rhodium-T.T. systems, complexation takes place on heating and the intensity of the colour becomes maximum and constant when the contents have been heated for an hour on a boiling water bath. Shape of the curves and λ_{max} of complexes remained unchanged even if the reactants were present in different ratios, showing thereby, the formation of a single complex in each case. Palladium-T.T. complexation was studied in cold as heating does not alter the absorbance. All the complexes were found to be stable for a considerable span of time (24 hours), after which measurements were discontinued.

In case of osmium(VIII) maintenance of 50% (v/v) acetone medium was necessary because the complex gets precipitated below this concentration. However, palladium(II) and rhodium(III) complexes were studied by extracting the complexes formed into chloroform, which was found to be most suitable among the commonly used solvents.

Physicochemical characteristics of the complexes : Various physicochemical characteristics viz., composition, adherence to Beer's law, conditions for the formation of complexes etc. have been summarised in Table 1.

Extraction behaviour : The extraction behaviour of rhodium and palladium thiotropolone complexes as a function of pH was studied by varying the pH's of the aqueous phases to different values and then extracting with 10 ml of freshly distilled chloroform.

* To whom correspondence should be addressed.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE COMPLEXES

S.No.	Characteristics	Rh(III)-T.T.	Pd(II)-T.T.	Os(VIII)-T.T.
1.	Colour	Brown	Red	Brownish red
2.	λ_{\max} (nm)	500	520	540
3.	pH-range for constant absorbing	7.0-8.0	3.0-7.5	3.0-5.5
4.	Molar excess of reagent per mole of metal ion	50	4	30
5.	Adherence to Beer's law	0.0-4.1 ppm	0.0-13.8 ppm	0.0-4.6 ppm
6.	Sensitivity (Sandell's Definition)	0.004 $\mu\text{g Rh/cm}^2$	0.018 $\mu\text{g Pd/cm}^2$	0.0148 $\mu\text{g Os/cm}^2$
7.	Molar Absorptivity	2.57×10^4	5.9×10^3	1.28×10^4
8.	Optimum range for accurate determination	0.79-3.55 ppm	2.63-13.0 ppm	0.65-4.1 ppm
9.	Composition M : L	1 : 3	1 : 2	1 : 2

The results of the study have been summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EXTRACTION BEHAVIOUR OF RHODIUM AND PALLADIUM-THIOTROPOLONE COMPLEXES. PERCENTAGE EXTRACTION AS A FUNCTION OF pH

pH	% Extraction	pH	% Extraction
(i) Rhodium-T.T. Complex			
2.0	40.0	7.0	100.0
4.5	55.9	7.5	100.0
5.6	75.0	8.0	100.0
6.6	93.4	8.4	60.0
		9.0	43.5
(ii) Palladium-T.T. Complex			
2.0	80.0	5.0	100.0
2.5	86.6	7.5	100.0
2.7	93.3	8.0	96.6
3.0	100.0	8.6	86.6

Recommended procedure

On the basis of the above investigations, following procedures are recommended for the determination of each metal :

Palladium (II) : To a suitable aliquot containing 26.3-130 μg of palladium(II), add an excess of acetone solution of thiotropolone (1 ml of $5 \times 10^{-3} M$). Adjust the pH between 3.0-7.5 by means of acetate buffer or NaOH and make up the volume to 10 ml. Extract the complex into 10 ml of chloroform, shake the mixture for five minutes on a shaking machine and set aside to attain equilibrium. Separate the organic layer, centrifuge to remove any water droplets and measure the absorbance of the complex at 520 nm against the corresponding reagent blank. Deduce the palladium content in the solution from the calibration curve drawn under similar conditions.

Rhodium (III) : To a suitable aliquot containing 8.0-35 μg of rhodium in 50 ml Corning glass bottle, add an excess of thiotropolone (2 ml of $1 \times 10^{-2} M$) solution and adjust the pH of the solution to 7.5 by means of dil. NaOH. Dilute the solution to 10 ml and heat it on a boiling water bath for about 1 hr. Cool the solution to room temperature and extract with 10 ml of chloroform. Keep the solution for 5 min. so that the organic phase is separated and the system attains equilibrium. Measure the extinction at 500 nm against the corresponding reagent blank. Find the amount of rhodium from a calibration curve drawn under identical conditions.

Osmium (VIII) : To a suitable aliquot containing 6.5 to 40.0 μg of osmium add an excess of thiotropolone solution in acetone (2 ml of $1 \times 10^{-2} M$). Maintain the pH of the solution at 4.5 with acetate buffer. Dilute the solution to 10 ml, heat the contents for one hour on a water bath, cool to room temperature, make up the volume to 10 ml again, maintaining 50% (v/v) acetone concentration and measure the absorbance at 540 nm against the corresponding reagent blank. Find the amount of osmium in solution from a calibration curve drawn under identical conditions.

Results and Discussion

Effect of diverse ions : To add to the usefulness of the method, the effect of various anions and cations was investigated in detail. It is seen that EDTA and cyanide cause serious interference even when present in traces inhibiting the colour formation. The results of this study are summarised in the table 3.

Determination of Rhodium in the presence of Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(III), Cu(II) and Pd(II) : To a solution containing 40 μg of rhodium and 100 μg of cobalt or nickel, an excess of thiotropolone in acetone (2 ml of $5 \times 10^{-2} M$), was added. pH was adjusted to 7.5 by means of dilute sodium hydroxide and the

TABLE 3—TOLERANCE LIMITS OF DIVERSE IONS

Ions added	Tolerance limits in ppm		
	Rh(III)-T.T. complex	Pd(II)-T.T. complex	Os(VIII)-T.T. complex
Bromide	2000	1000	1000
Iodide	1000	200	500
Nitrate	5000	5000	5000
Sulphate	5000	2000	5000
Phosphate	500	1000	500
Sulphite	400	Interferes seriously	150
Thiocyanate	400	1000	100
Nitrite	150	600	Interferes seriously
Tartrate	100	1000	100
Thiourea	100	1000	Interferes
Fluoride	100	2000	200
Thiosulphate	500	Interferes seriously	Interferes
Citrate	Interferes seriously	1000	100
Oxalate	-do-	Interferes seriously	100
Zn(II)	20	15	20
Cd(II)	20	20	20
Hg(II)	40*F'(500)	50*F'(500)	40*F'(500)
V(V)	10	50*F'(1000)	10
Mo(VI)	20	50	10
Sb(III)	10	20	15
In(III)	10	25	15
Ga(III)	20	20	20
Pb(II)	20	100	50
Sn(IV)	20*F'(80)	50	50
Ba(II), Ca(II), Sr(II), Mg(II)	500 each	500 each	500 each
Rh(III)	—	15	Interferes
Pd(II)	20**	—	5**
Pt(IV)	Interferes	30	30**
Ru(III)	5**	20	5*
Ir(IV)	5**	50	10
Os(VIII)	Interferes	40	—
Mn(II)	10	30	20
Cu(II)	20**	10*F.U.(100)	10**

* masked with anion indicated (in ppm).

** removed by selective extraction in cold.

volume of aqueous phase was raised to 10 ml. The resulting mixture was extracted with 10 ml of chloroform. The Co(II) or Ni(II) complex was quantitatively extracted under these conditions while rhodium remained in aqueous phase. 5 ml of the aqueous solution was then taken in a 50 ml glass stoppered

bottle and 2 ml of $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ thiotropolone solution was added. The volume was raised to 10 ml and the contents were heated on a water bath for about 60 mins. After cooling to room temperature, the rhodium complex was extracted into 10 ml of chloroform. The absorbance of the chloroform extract was measured at 500 nm and rhodium content was deduced from the calibration curve.

In case of iron the pH was adjusted to 6.0 and the complex was extracted into chloroform. Copper or palladium were removed by adjusting the pH to 3.5 and extracting the complexes in chloroform.

Using the above procedure, 2 ppm of rhodium could be satisfactorily determined in presence of 10 ppm each of iron, cobalt, nickel and palladium and 20 ppm of copper.

Conclusion

Thiotropolone ranks amongst the most sensitive reagents known for rhodium. Rhodium can be determined in presence of large number of common metal ions (mentioned above). As most of them which form coloured complexes in cold can be extracted selectively. Palladium on the other hand can be determined selectively in presence of other platinum metals, as it undergoes complexation in cold. Osmium can also be determined in presence of platinum(IV) as the former is not extracted in chloroform at all.

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